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Applying an Agent-based Distributed AI Framework to Forecast Power for the Mini-Grid Stability

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Abstract—Renewable energy sources, expected to form about 70% of power systems by 2050, bring challenges like fluctuating outputs and grid instability. Advanced power monitoring systems, crucial in environments like research facilities and hospitals, must navigate these dynamic scenarios. Traditional power management, especially Uninterruptible Power Supply (UPS) systems, often needs to catch up due to high costs and limited response to varied power demands, focusing mainly on constant power supply without differentiating between constant and fluctuating loads. In response, Artificial intelligence (AI) techniques are becoming indispensable for real-time power prediction and control. A distributed AI framework forecasts power needs, considering renewable sources, loads, and storage. This is key to ensuring smooth mini-grid operations, balancing operational demands with environmental considerations, and advancing intelligent energy management. Such systems are essential in optimizing energy usage, aligning it with available power to enhance efficiency and reduce waste. This is particularly important for mini-grids, with or without UPS systems, where predictive monitoring can substantially cut operational costs and extend lifespan.

The paper focuses on providing consistent, constant, and fluctuating power by predicting mini-grid power needs hourly from the previous day’s data. We use a Temporal Convolutional Network (TCN) for time series prediction, integrated within the BDIx agent’s belief system through TensorFlow Lite. This approach accurately predicts upcoming power needs, ensures smooth operation, and prevents power outages. The TCN model’s predictive capabilities highlight a significant stride in combining AI with energy management to address the complexities of modern power systems.

Index Terms—Distributed AI, power fluctuations, distributed power sources, distributed power loads, constant power load prediction, fluctuating power prediction, power control.

I. INTRODUCTION

Despite their low environmental impact, renewable energy sources such as wind turbines and solar systems challenge power grid stability due to unpredictable fluctuations. This unpredictability and varying consumption patterns necessitate advanced prediction strategies for fluctuating and constant power devices to maintain system stability. As renewables integrate alongside electricity demand, the importance of accurate prediction models for grid stability and quality becomes more pronounced. Power monitoring systems are critical in this context, particularly in essential services like research

institutions and hospitals. These systems, crucial in diverse settings, including households, predict power usage and optimize energy utilization through real-time data and analytics, enhancing efficiency and reducing waste. They are key in managing backup systems like UPS, balancing reliability with cost, and essential for emergency readiness and sustainability, supporting renewable integration and reducing carbon footprint.

To meet these challenges, artificial intelligence (AI) becomes vital for real-time power control and prediction. A distributed AI framework is crucial for accurately predicting power system needs, considering renewable sources, loads, and storage. This is essential for stable mini-grid operations, especially as renewables replace controlled sources. Efficient communication and smart power control are necessary to balance power supply and demand, facilitating sustainable energy transitions. Building on [1], this work focuses on ensuring smooth power delivery by predicting mini-grid power needs hourly using the prior day’s data. Using a TCN time series model for regression [2], implemented in TensorFlow Lite within the BDIx agent’s system on Raspberry Pi, it forecasts the next hour’s power needs with high precision, aiming for uninterrupted operations and avoiding outages.

a) Contributions and Outlines: In the realm of energy management, the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques, while extensive in other fields, often remains confined to initial evaluations and solving specific problems within centralized systems. This study broadens the scope by enhancing the Distributed AI (DAI) framework, as mentioned in [1], to effectively regulate and predict power in mini-grids, ensuring a steady power flow. The framework utilizes distributed BDI (Belief-Desire-Intention) agents, augmented with machine learning capabilities, to efficiently manage various power generators, loads, and storage devices. These BDIx agents are versatile, adaptable to different power system elements, and focus on ML-driven optimization of power distribution through constant and fluctuating power prediction.

The approach is characterized by its AI/ML distributed autonomous system aimed at accurate power prediction and ensuring smooth operations within the mini-grid. It incorporates Temporal Convolutional Networks (TNC) to forecast immediate future power requirements, including constant and fluctuating loads. The framework employs Fuzzy logic to prioritize Desires in line with Intentions, with a steadfast focus on maintaining uninterrupted power flow as a paramount

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Fig. 1: Agent-based distributed AI framework for power prediction belief. Additionally, it is designed to swiftly adapt to changing power demands, addressing fluctuations in load, power events, and threshold violations, such as energy and device capacity limitations, ensuring comprehensive and responsive energy management.

II. AGENT-BASED DAI FRAMEWORK UTILIZING ML FOR PREDICTING POWER USAGE

This research utilized the BDix agent-based DAI framework (shown in [1]) embedded with power usage prediction aimed to ensure the power-stability and safe operation of the power system against the power fluctuations caused by generators and loads as shown in Fig 1. The novelty of this approach is that it deploys a BDix agent in the main board of the house, and it is responsible for informing the other agents that are hosted on the fluctuating power sources and constant power sources for the constant and fluctuating needs for the next hour. Each agent is responsible for communicating and controlling functionalities.

a) Belief Desire Intention eXtended Agents for Power Prediction: The BDix agents' functionality comprises their Beliefs, Desires, Goals, Intentions, Behavior, and Plan Library. The description of the additional components (from [1]) to achieve the prediction tasks is shown below: i) for Beliefs the "two TCN models", one that will predict the next hour constant load and the other to predict the fluctuating load and the "two double list variables called 24HoursConstantLoad and 24HoursFluctuatingLoad", one that keeps the current constant load for a day and a second that keeps the current fluctuating load for a day; ii) for Desires the desire "Predict the Next Hour Constant and Fluctuating Load ". For Intentions and Goals, the desire above is always an Intention and in the Goals with 100% priority. Thus, in the Fuzzy Logic Plan Library, there is a rule that in any event, the Desire, as mentioned earlier, always gets 100% priority. The existing BDix agent can collaborate with the agents in the Constant and Fluctuating Power sources and request power increase or reduction. Because BDix agents communicate, exchanging information to adapt actions, learning from peers, and teaching others to execute specific tasks.

b) Simulation Results: We have categorized the power consumption dataset from [3] in our analysis based on the types of power sources and loads. We have distinguished between constant and fluctuating types. The dataset, comprising hourly measurements, has been methodically classified daily

(24 hours). The classification is crucial for our study because it allows us to efficiently examine and use the most up-to-date load data for predictive modeling, focusing on the newest trends and patterns in power usage.

Table I with Figures 2 and 3 showcases the performance of two models using a Temporal Convolutional Network (TCN) for predicting fluctuating and constant loads. The Fluctuating Loads Model has a lower Mean Squared Error (MSE) of 38,591.55 compared to the Constant Loads Model's 162,436.85, indicating higher variability in the latter's predictions. Both models, however, demonstrate high accuracy with very low MSE percentages. The Constant Loads Model has a higher Mean Absolute Error (MAE) at 351.60, suggesting less precision in average predictions than the Fluctuating Loads Model, which has an MAE of 168.16. Despite this, the Constant Loads Model slightly surpasses the Fluctuating Loads Model in R-squared values, suggesting a better fit to the data. The Fluctuating Loads Model has a slightly higher Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), yet both models exhibit strong predictive capabilities, as evidenced by their high Explained Variance Scores. The Constant Loads Model also records a higher Max Error, indicating greater worst-case prediction errors. In summary, while the Fluctuating Loads Model generally shows lower prediction errors, the Constant Loads Model demonstrates a marginally better data fit.

TABLE I: TCN Model Results for Predicting Fluctuating and Constant Loads

Metric	Fluctuating Loads Model	Constant Loads Model
MSE	38591.55	162436.85
MSE (%)	0.0002	0.0001
MAE	168.16	351.60
R2	0.999979	0.999989
MAPE	0.09257	0.08405
Explained Variance Score	0.999993	0.999996
Max Error	490.03	937.59

Fig. 2: Real vs Predicted - Constant Loads

Fig. 3: Real vs Predicted - Fluctuating Loads

III. CONCLUDING REMARKS

This research tackles the challenge of balancing power requests in systems with renewable energy sources, introducing a novel agent-based Distributed AI (DAI) framework for predicting both constant and fluctuating power needs. Utilizing daily-categorized power consumption data, our approach highlights the DAI framework's architecture and the proficiency of BDix agents in managing the variability of renewable energy, thereby improving power system stability.

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